

TRANSFORMING HEALTH THROUGH AYURVEDA

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ABSTRACT

Ayurveda, an ancient holistic system of medicine, emphasizes balance of *Doshas*, *Dhatus*, *Malas*, *Agni*, and *Ojas* for sustaining health. In the modern era, rapid industrialization, pollution, nutritional deficiencies, and lifestyle irregularities have contributed substantially to the global rise in non-communicable diseases (NCDs). With lifestyle disorders now responsible for over 60% of deaths in India, there is a renewed interest in *Ayurveda's* preventive and promotive health strategies. This study explores classical *Ayurveda* principles that can support health transformation in contemporary contexts.

KEYWORDS: *Ayurveda*, Health, *Dosha*, Equilibrium, Fundamentals.**INTRODUCTION**

Ayurveda, one of the world's oldest systems of medicine, provides a comprehensive approach for maintaining health and managing diseases. *Acharyas* of *Ayurveda* have described numerous principles and regimens in classical texts for promoting well-being and preventing illness. In the modern age, rapid industrialization, urbanization, global warming, environmental pollution, nutritional deficiencies, and mental stress have contributed to an increased incidence of both pathogenic and non-pathogenic diseases. These challenges necessitate the revival and practical application of *Ayurveda* principles, which are effective, affordable, and holistic in nature.

and nutrient assimilation. Conversely, *Agni*-damaging foods such as heavy, oily, cold, and incompatible items—like curd at night, refrigerated food, excess sweets, or overeating—impair digestion, causing *Ama* (toxins) and metabolic imbalance. In *Grishma* (summer), light and cooling foods like barley, rice gruel, and green gram pacify *Pitta*, while in *Hemanta* (winter), strengthening foods like milk, wheat, *Ghee*, and dates enhance *Agni*, promote *Dhatu Poshana*, and sustain vitality.^[5]

2. Concept of Immunity (*Ojas* and *Vyadhi-Kshamatva*)

Ayurveda describes *Para* and *Apara Ojas* as determinants of vitality and immunity. *Vyadhi-Bala-Virodhitva* and *Vyadhyutpada-Pratibandhakatva* represent resistance to disease.

Immunity can be enhanced through *Ritucharya*, *Dinacharya*, *Sadvritta*, *Rasayana* therapy, and proper *Panchakarma* protocols like *Sansarjana Krama*.

In *Ayurveda*, immunity is the manifestation of *Dhatu Samyata* (tissue equilibrium) and *Ojas*—the vital essence of all *Dhatu*s responsible for strength and disease resistance.^[6] *Ojas* pervades the entire body^[7] and serves as a protective shield against physical, biological, and psychological stressors. It exists in two forms: *Para Ojas*, seated in the *Hrudaya* and essential for life (*Pranayatana*), and *Apara Ojas*, the circulating essence nourishing tissues daily.^[8]

Impaired *Ojas* formation due to poor diet, stress, or *Ama* accumulation leads to reduced *Bala* (strength) and vulnerability to disease.

Vyadhikshamatva—*Ayurveda* immunity—has two aspects: *Vyadhiutpada Pratibandhakatva* (prevention of disease occurrence) and *Vyadhi Bala Virodhitva* (resistance to disease progression), comparable to innate and adaptive immunity.^[9] True immunity, as per *Ayurveda*, arises from a balanced state of body, mind, and spirit maintained through *Ritucharya*, *Dinacharya*, and *Sadvritta*.

Rasayana Chikitsa is a specialized *Ayurveda* therapy aimed at rejuvenating and strengthening *Dhatu*s, thereby enhancing *Ojas* and overall immunity. *Acharya Charaka* described *Rasayana* as that which promotes longevity, intelligence, memory, complexion, and disease resistance. *Rasayana* drugs like *Amalaki*, *Guduchi*, *Ashwagandha*, and *Shatavari* nourish the body at the cellular level, improve metabolism, and delay tissue degeneration.^[10]

For *Rasayana* therapy to be effective, *Shodhana* (purification) through *Panchakarma* is

essential to eliminate *Ama* and prepare the body for rejuvenation.^[11] Thus, *Ayurveda*'s immunological approach integrates nutrition, detoxification, and rejuvenation, aiming not only to prevent disease but to sustain *Swasthya* (health) through the preservation and enhancement of *Ojas*.

3. Management of Obesity (*Sthaulya*)

In *Sthaulya*, *Medovaha* and *Rasavaha Srotas* are primarily involved, with secondary involvement of *Mamsavaha* and *Udakavaha Srotas*. Blockage and excessive nourishment of these channels lead to accumulation of *Meda* and sluggish *Agni*. Management focuses on restoring *srotas* patency and metabolic fire through *Langhana*, *Lekhana*, *Shodhana*, and *Shamana* therapies, such as Administration of *Takrarishta*, *Madhu* (honey), *Vidanga* (*Embelia ribes*), *Nagara* (*Zingiber officinale*), *Yavakshara*, *Amlaki* (*Emblia officinalis*), and *Shilajatu*.^[12]

Use of *Vrihat Panchamula* and *Ruksha Abhyanga* (unctuous-less massage).

Pathya Ahara (wholesome diet) includes green gram (*Mudga*), barley (*Yava*), horse gram (*Kulatha*), buttermilk (*Takra*), honey water, and light, non-unctuous foods. *Apathya Ahara* comprises fried foods, sweets, curd, excessive milk, day sleep, and sedentary habits. Exercise and *Yoga* play a vital role; *Surya Namaskar*, *Trikonasana*, *Ardha Matsyendrasana*, *Pavanamuktasana*, and *Bhujangasana* help reduce abdominal fat and improve metabolism.^[13]

Modern studies support the efficacy of *Triphala Guggul*, *Navaka Guggulu*, *Vrihat Panchamula*, and *Panchakarma* therapies like *Virechana* and *Udvardana* in obesity.^[14] Thus, *Ayurveda* offers a holistic, sustainable approach to obesity by balancing *Doshas*, enhancing *Agni*, clearing *Srotas*, and promoting overall health and vitality.

4. Bloodletting (*Raktamokshana*)

Raktamokshana, one of the major *Shodhana* (purificatory) therapies of *Ayurveda*, plays a vital role in eliminating *Dushta Rakta* (vitiated blood) and maintaining internal homeostasis. It purifies the bloodstream, improves microcirculation, clears *Srotorodha* (obstructions in channels), and restores equilibrium of *Pitta* and *Rakta Dosh*.^[15] By doing so, it prevents the accumulation of toxins (*Ama*) and maintains the normal functioning of all tissues and organs.

Bloodletting is advised for purification and detoxification of vitiated *Rakta*. As *Sharad Ritu* (autumn) predisposes to *Rakta Dushti*, bloodletting at this time removes excess heat and impure blood, thereby preventing *Rakta-pradoshaja vyadhis* and seasonal diseases.^[16] It can

be performed through *Siravedha*, *Jalaukavacharana* (leech therapy), or *Shringa* and *Alabu* methods, depending on the condition.^[15]

This therapy is especially beneficial for individuals of *Pitta* or *Rakta-Pradhana Prakriti*, and is indicated in diseases like *Kushtha* (skin disorders), *Vatarakta* (gout), *Visarpa* (erysipelas), *Raktapitta* (bleeding disorders), *Siragranthi* (varicose veins), *Netra roga*, and *Sandhigata Vata* (joint inflammation).^[16] It should be avoided in persons with low strength, anemia, dehydration, pregnancy, childhood, or old age.^[17]

Beyond treating diseases, *Raktamokshana* transforms health by detoxifying the blood, enhancing oxygenation, and improving metabolic activity. It strengthens immunity, revitalizes the skin, enhances mental clarity, and sustains overall vitality.^[18] Thus, it serves both preventive and curative functions, supporting holistic health through purification, balanced *Doshas*, and rejuvenation of the body and mind.

5. Principles of Wholesome Diet (*Pathya-Apathya*)

Ayurveda places *Ahara* (diet) at the center of health maintenance, describing it as the foremost pillar of life (*Trayopastambha*).^[19] The concept of *Pathya–Apathya* food and regimen, forms the basis of preventive as well as curative healthcare.^[20]

The tenfold principles of wholesome food emphasize: hot, unctuous, moderate in quantity, taken at the proper time, non-contradictory to one's constitution and season, and consumed with mindfulness in a clean, calm environment, only after digestion of the previous meal.^[21]

Recent *Ayurveda* literature emphasizes that *Pathya* food enhances *Agni* (digestive fire), promotes *Dhatu poshana* (tissue nourishment), stabilizes *Doshas*, and strengthens *Ojas*, supports faster healing and enhances drug efficacy,^[22] it is the essence of vitality and immunity.^[23]

In contrast, *Apathya Ahara* disturbs these balances, leading to accumulation of *Ama* (toxins) and diseases such as obesity, diabetes, hypertension, skin disorders, and liver ailments. The principle also extends to *Vihara* (behavioral regimen), emphasizing moderation in sleep, physical activity, emotional balance, and cleanliness.^[24]

Modern interpretations relate these guidelines to mindful eating, chrono-nutrition, and gut–brain axis regulation.^[25] By aligning food with individual constitution (*Prakriti*), season (*Ritu*), and digestion capacity (*Agni*), *Ayurveda* promotes harmony between body and

mind.^[21]

Thus, *Pathya–Apathya* serves as a comprehensive lifestyle science ensuring preventive, promotive, and restorative health, demonstrating that right food taken in the right way truly acts as the best medicine.

6. *Langhana* Therapy (Lightening/Reduction Therapy)

Langhana is a controlled depletion strategy in classical therapeutics intended to reduce metabolic overload, kindle digestive fire (*Agni*), and restore physiological homeostasis.^[26]

Charaka enumerates ten modalities of *Langhana*: *Upavāsa* (therapeutic fasting), *Pachana* (use of digestive agents), *Vyāyāma* (therapeutic exercise), *Ātapa sevana* (regulated sun exposure), *Maruta sevana* (fresh-air regimen), *Pipāsa nigraha* (thirst restraint), *Kṣudha nigraha* (hunger restraint), *Laghu āhāra* (light diet), *Śodhana* (select purificatory measures used in mild form), and *Deepana* (appetizer therapy) — each selected according to *prakṛti*, *bala*, and *vikāra*.^[27] These modalities act via caloric restriction, enhanced autophagy, improved insulin sensitivity, reduced low-grade inflammation, and accelerated lipid mobilization, thereby benefitting *Kapha*- and *Meda*-dominant disorders such as obesity, *prameha*, dyslipidemia, and *Ama*-related febrile states.^[26]

Charaka classifies *Apatarpana* into three types: *Langhana* (depletion alone), *Langhana–Pachana* (depletion combined with metabolic/digestive agents), and *Doṣavasechana* (therapeutic elimination of vitiated *doṣas*); selection depends on the predominant pathophysiology and stage of disease.^[28] Indications include *Ama-sampurnata*, *Santarpanotttha Vyādhi* (overnutrition disorders), *Jvara*, *Aruci*, and *Ālasya*. Contraindications per *Charaka* comprise *Vātapradhānaya* conditions, marked *Dhātu-Kṣaya* (emaciation), pregnancy, extreme age or debility, and the immediate post-purificatory state—contexts in which further depletion risks iatrogenic tissue wasting or loss of *Ojas*.^[29] Clinical application mandates individualized dosing, staged implementation, and post-therapy dietary stabilization to avoid rebound pathology and preserve tissue integrity.^[30] This therapy can be Administered to everyone in *Hemanta* and *Shishira Ritus*.^[27] *Langhana* is beneficial in conditions like obesity, diabetes, *Ama Dosh*, fever, and skin diseases. It enhances digestive power, taste perception, lightness, and purity of mind and body.^[26]

7. Administration of *Mahakashayas*^[31,32]

Mahākāśayas are potent botanical groups delineated in representing pharmacological clusters designed to act synergistically on *Doṣa*, *Dhātu*, and *Srotas*. They serve as foundational formulations for purification (*Doṣa-śodhana*), rejuvenation (*Rasāyana*), and restoration of homeostasis.^[33] Among them, *Daśamūla* and *Pañcamūla* are extensively used for *Jvara*, *Śoṭha*, *Sandhivāta*, and *Prameha*, functioning through anti-inflammatory, antipyretic, antioxidant, and immunomodulatory pathways. Experimental studies confirm *Daśamūla*'s analgesic, anti-platelet, and hepatoprotective effects^[34] Phytochemical analyses show the presence of alkaloids, flavonoids, and saponins responsible for cytokine modulation and oxidative stress reduction.^[33] *Pañcamūla* variants such as *Laghupañcamūla* and *Kantaka Pañcamūla* exhibit diuretic, adaptogenic, and respiratory benefits, supporting their role in *Vāta-Kapha* disorders.^[35]

Other *Mahākāśayas*, including *Jīvanīya*, *Varnya*, and *Sandhānīya* groups, enhance complexion, wound healing, immunity, and *Ojas*^[33] These formulations embody the Ayurvedic principle of “*Sāmya Karaṇa*”—restoring equilibrium between catabolic and anabolic processes. Modern evaluations link *Daśamūla* and *Rasāyana* *Mahākāśayas* to improved glycemic control, lipid modulation, and mitochondrial resilience.^[36]

Collectively, *Mahākāśayas* bridge classical pharmaco-therapeutics and modern phytomedicine, serving as multi-targeted interventions for metabolic, inflammatory, and degenerative disorders—thereby transforming health from imbalance to dynamic equilibrium and vitality.

8. Rejuvenation (*Rasayana*) and Aphrodisiac (*Vajikarana*) Therapies

Rasayana and *Vajikarana* are two significant branches of *Ayurveda* that focus on revitalizing body and mind while enhancing reproductive health. *Rasayana* Chikitsa aims to promote longevity, delay aging, strengthen immunity, and improve physical and mental vigor.

Vajikarana Chikitsa supports fertility, virility, and sexual vitality. Both therapies are recommended after proper purification (*Shodhana*) of the body channels to ensure optimal absorption and efficacy.^[11]

Recent scientific studies have explored these classical concepts through pharmacological and clinical research. *Rasayana* formulations such as *Dhatryadi Rasayana*, *Ashwagandha* (*Withania Somnifera*), *Amalaki* (*Embllica Officinalis*), and *Guduchi* (*Tinospora Cordifolia*)

have demonstrated potent antioxidant, immunomodulatory, and adaptogenic effects.^[37,38]

A 2024 scoping review highlighted that many *Rasayana* herbs act as biological adaptogens, improving resilience against stress and supporting cellular repair mechanisms. Experimental and clinical studies indicate potential benefits in immunity enhancement, anti-aging, neuroprotection, and even as supportive therapy in chronic diseases and oncology.^[39]

Similarly, *Vajikarana* therapy has been validated through modern research for its aphrodisiac and fertility-enhancing properties. Classical *Vajikarana* herbs such as *Kaunch Beej* (*Mucuna Pruriens*), *Safed Musli* (*Chlorophytum Borivilianum*), *Gokshura* (*Tribulus Terrestris*), and *Shatavari* (*Asparagus Racemosus*) have shown promising effects on sexual behavior, sperm quality, and hormonal balance.^[40] Clinical trials and preclinical studies, including those on *Kaamdev Ghrita* and *Vajikarana* food preparations, report improvements in libido, semen parameters, and overall vitality.^[41]

9. Theory of Natural Homeostasis

Ayurveda defines health (*Swasthya*) as a state of equilibrium among doshas (functional energies), *Dhatus* (tissues), and *Malas* (waste products), maintained by balanced *Agni* (metabolism) and a calm, stable mind.^[42] This harmony, called *Dhatu Samyata*, represents the natural rhythm of the body. Any disturbance in this balance due to improper diet, erratic lifestyle, stress, or environmental changes results in disease, while restoration of equilibrium naturally re-establishes health^[43]—reflecting the body's innate healing intelligence (*Svabhava-Sansiddhi Shakti*).^[44]

This concept parallels the modern scientific theory of homeostasis, where the body sustains internal stability through self-regulating mechanisms. Both systems recognize that health is not a static condition but a dynamic, adaptive process. *Ayurveda* views *Vata*, *Pitta* and *Kapha* as regulatory forces governing movement, transformation, and stability. When these are balanced, the tissues are nourished, wastes are eliminated, and the body functions efficiently, maintaining resilience and immunity.

Ayurveda emphasizes that the human organism possesses an inherent ability to heal itself when supported by proper conditions. Practices such as *Dinacharya* (daily regimen), *Ritucharya* (seasonal discipline), *Ahara Vidhi* (wholesome diet), *Shodhana* (purification therapies), and *Rasayana* (rejuvenation) strengthen this self-healing mechanism. The balance

between the inner environment (*Purusha*) and the outer universe (*Loka*) ensures sustained vitality and adaptability.

Thus, the theory of natural homeostasis in Ayurveda integrates physical, psychological, and spiritual harmony. It upholds that true health arises from the body's intrinsic power to restore equilibrium, demonstrating Ayurveda's holistic vision of natural healing and continuous self-renewal.

10. Destruction as a Passive Phenomenon

Ayurveda perceives destruction not as an active process but as the cessation of causative influences, implying that disease and death occur when life-sustaining factors lose efficacy.

The *Ayurveda's* model of health transformation integrates physical, mental, and spiritual dimensions. Its preventive emphasis through *Dinacharya*, *Ritucharya*, and dietary discipline provides a practical framework for modern lifestyle disorders.

Unlike symptomatic modern treatments, *Ayurveda* targets the root cause by harmonizing *Doshas*, improving *Agni*, and nourishing *Dhatus*. Therapies like *Langhana*, *Rasayana*, and *Vajikarana* highlight *Ayurveda's* potential in regenerative and lifestyle medicine.

CONCLUSION

Ayurveda offers timeless wisdom for transforming health through balance, prevention, and rejuvenation. Its integrative principles, when applied in modern contexts, can effectively combat lifestyle disorders, metabolic imbalances, and immune deficiencies.

Lifestyle diseases are the health conditions caused by improper daily regimens and poor lifestyles choices, and by opting ayurveda into daily routine, it pacifies such poor health conditions by individualized care, self-awareness and natural healing, aligning with global health goals and WHO vision "Health for All" .

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